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EXISTENCE OF SOLUTIONS OF STOCHASTIC DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS IN FINANCE

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Abstract:

Stochastic differential equations (SDEs) have become standard models for financial quantities such as asset prices, interest rates, and their derivatives. To give an example from financial mathematics, the classical model for a stock price is that of a geometric Brownian motion. In this paper, an introduction to the theory of stochastic differential equations (SDE) is given and have shown how this theory can be useful in financial modeling. The following main topics are included: concept of Brownian motion, stochastic integrals, its formula, stochastic differential equations, applications to the Black-Scholes model. The aim is to solve a particular financial problem, namely that of finding the correct price of a European call option.

Keywords: *Brownian motion, Stochastic differential equations, Ito integral, Black-scholes model*

Introduction:

Stochastic differential equations are used to describe the dynamics of a wide variety of random phenomena in physical, biological, engineering and social sciences. The processes of financial mathematics in conditions of (B; S)-market is patterned by stochastic differential equations Ito. Wars, decisions of the Federal Reserve and other central banks, and other news can cause the stock price to make a sudden shift. To model this, one would like to represent the stock price by a process that has jumps. Some results on stochastic differential equations can be found in [1] and [2]. Applications of SDE solvers to Monte-Carlo sampling for financial pricing of derivatives and the discussion on the extension of SDE solvers to coupled systems driven by correlated noise, which is applicable to multiple asset markets were done by [7]

Let $X(t)$ denotes the price of one unit of a given asset at time t . The dynamics of the asset price can be assumed to have a deterministic part, depending on the interest rate, and a stochastic part, depending on fluctuations in the market. This feature of the dynamics makes it useful to model asset prices by stochastic differential equations. Due to the stochastic nature of the asset price dynamics, the price of the asset at a fixed future time T is unknown. Nevertheless, based on realistic models for the asset price dynamics, we will be able to draw conclusions regarding the future price of the asset and based on these conclusions the price of options and other financial derivatives can be determined.

A typical one-dimensional stochastic differential equation is of the form

$$dX_t = \sigma(X_t) dB_t - b(X_t)dt,$$

where dB_t is the differential of a one-dimensional Brownian motion, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ and $b(\cdot)$ are functions of R

Definition :

A European call option gives its owner the right, without obligation, to buy one unit of a particular asset at a pre-specified price K at some fixed future time T . If the price of the asset at time T is lower than K , the option will not be exercised and its value is zero. If, on the other hand, the price of the asset at time T exceeds K , the owner of the option may buy one unit of the asset at price K and immediately sell at price $X(T)$, hence gaining a profit of $X(T) - K$. Conclusively, the payoff of the option is

$$(X(T) - K)^+ := X(T) - K ; \text{ if } X(T) > K; \\ 0 ; \text{ if } X(T) \leq K;$$

Given that the price of one unit of the asset at time t is x , we would be able to determine the arbitrage free price of a European call option for a specified choice of K and T . By arbitrage free, we mean that neither the seller nor the buyer of the option are allowed to gain money with probability one. In order to determine the price, we need the following:

1. Mathematical techniques to handle the price dynamics: Stochastic calculus.
2. A mathematical model for the price process: The Black-Scholes equation.

Stochastic processes

We model the price $X(t)$ of the asset as a stochastic process. A stochastic process X is a collection of random variables. More precisely, for every $t \in [0; \infty)$, $X(t) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a random variable corresponding to some infinite set of outcomes Ω . For every possible outcome $\omega \in \Omega$, the stochastic process gives rise to a trajectory $X\omega : [0; \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Hence a stochastic process can be viewed as an infinite sample of trajectories evolving randomly over time. We write the stochastic process as a function $X : [0; \infty) \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where the randomness of X is determined by the choice of $\omega \in \Omega$. Here we consider the stochastic process X to be a Markov process, which means that given the present value of the process, the future behaviour of X is independent of the past values of X . In financial terms this can be interpreted as all past information being incorporated in the present price of the asset. This property, known as market efficiency, is a reasonable assumption.

Wiener process:

A Wiener process $W : [0; \infty) \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, is a Gaussian stochastic process with independent increments for which

1. $W(0) = 0$ with probability 1;
2. $E[W(t) - W(s)] = 0$;
3. $E[(W(t) - W(s))^2] = t - s$

Brownian motion:

Let (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) be a probability space equipped with a filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_t : t \geq 0\}$. A d -dimensional (\mathcal{F}_t) -adapted stochastic process $\{B_t : t \geq 0\}$ is called an (\mathcal{F}_t) -Brownian motion provided

- (A) the paths $t \rightarrow B_t(\omega)$ are continuous;
- (B) for every $t > r \geq 0$, $B_t - B_r$ is independent of the σ -algebra \mathcal{F}_r ;
- (C) for every $t > r \geq 0$, $B_t - B_r$ is normally distributed with mean zero and covariance matrix $(t - r)Id$, where Id is the $d \times d$ identity matrix.

Stochastic integrals : Let $\mu(t, x)$ and $\sigma(t, x)$ be two functions which will be referred to as the drift and diffusion coefficients, respectively. The stochastic process X is a stochastic differential equation if its local dynamics is

$$dX(t) = \mu(t, X(t)) dt + \sigma(t, X(t)) dW(t), \tag{1}$$

with initial condition $X(0) = X_0$. This means that during the time interval $[t, t + dt]$ the

process X is driven by a locally deterministic velocity $\mu(t, X(t))$ and an independent Gaussian disturbance term amplified by the factor $\sigma(t, X(t))$. If we divide both sides formally by dt , we obtain the differential equation

$$\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = \mu(t, X(t)) + \sigma(t, X(t))\xi(t), \tag{2}$$

Where $\xi(t) = dW(t)/dt$ is the formal time derivative of a Wiener process. But as we noted above, a Wiener process is nowhere differentiable and hence ξ does not exist. Instead we integrate (1) and obtain

$$X(t) = X_0 + \int_0^t \mu(s, X(s))ds + \int_0^t \sigma(s, X(s))dw(s), \tag{3}$$

The leftmost integral is a Riemann integral for each trajectory of X , but the righthmost integral is not even a Lebesgue-Stieltjes integral, since the continuous trajectories of a Wiener process can be shown to vary infinitely on any bounded time interval. We need a new theory for this stochastic integral (also known as an Itô integral). The main restriction on the integrands $\sigma(t, x)$ in the Itô integral is that they are only allowed to depend on the past and present behaviour of the weiner process.

Theorem (Itô formula) : Let X be a stochastic differential equation given by

$$dX(t) = \mu(t, X(t))dt + \sigma(t, X(t))dw(t) \tag{4}$$

and let $U: [0, T] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a two times continuously differentiable function. Then $Y(t) = U(t, X(t))$ is a stochastic differential equation given by

$$dY(t) = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial t}(t, X(t)) + \mu(t, X(t)) \frac{\partial U}{\partial x}(t, X(t)) + \frac{1}{2} \sigma(t, X(t))^2 \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2}(t, X(t)) \right) dt + \sigma(t, X(t)) \frac{\partial U}{\partial x}(t, X(t)) dw(t) \tag{5}$$

We derive the solution to the stochastic differential equation

$$dX(t) = a(t)X(t)dt + b(t)X(t)dw(t), \tag{6}$$

known as geometric Brownian motion. This is a stochastic counterpart to the exponential growth model

$$\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = a(t)X(t); \tag{7}$$

which has the solution $X(T) = X(0) \exp \left(\int_0^T a(t)dt \right)$

As a consequence, we expect the solution to (6) to be a randomly disturbed exponential function.

Indeed, dividing both sides of (6) by $X(t)$ and integrating, we obtain

$$\frac{dX(t)}{X(t)} = a(t)dt + b(t)dw(t) \Rightarrow \int_0^T \frac{dX(t)}{X(t)} = \int_0^T a(t)dt + \int_0^T b(t)dw(t) \tag{8}$$

Guided by the form of the integral term on the left hand side of the second equality of (8), we apply the Itô formula to the function

$$U(t, X(t)) = \log X(t) \tag{9}$$

and arrive at

$$d(\log X(t)) = \frac{\partial U}{\partial t}(t, X(t))dt + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x}(t, X(t)) dx(t) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2}(t, X(t))(dX(t))^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 0 + \frac{1}{X(t)} dX(t) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{-1}{X(t)} \right)^2 (dX(t))^2 \\
 &= \frac{dX(t)}{X(t)} - \frac{(b(t)X(t))^2}{2X(t)^2} dt = \frac{dX(t)}{X(t)} - \frac{(b(t))^2}{2} dt \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\int_0^T \frac{dX(t)}{X(t)} = \int_0^T d(\log X(t)) + \int_0^T \frac{(b(t))^2}{2} dt = \log \frac{X(T)}{X(0)} + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T (b(t))^2 dt \tag{11}$$

Combining (8) and (11)

$$\log \frac{X(T)}{X(0)} = \int_0^T a(t) dt + \int_0^T b(t) dw(t) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T (b(t))^2 dt \tag{12}$$

or

$$X(T) = X(0) \exp \left(\int_0^T \left(a(t) - \frac{1}{2} (b(t))^2 \right) dt + \int_0^T b(t) dw(t) \right) \tag{13}$$

which in the special case of constant a and b reduces to

$$X(T) = X(0) \exp \left(\left(a - \frac{1}{2} b^2 \right) T + b w(T) \right) \tag{14}$$

One can show that $E [X (T)] = E [X (0)] \exp \int_0^T a(t) dt$

hence the expectation of X (T) coincides with the solution to the deterministic model of exponential growth.

The Blach-Scholes Equation:

Geometric Brownian motion is often used to model the price of the share. Let X(t). Denote the price of one unit of a given share on time t and suppose that the price dynamics of the share is given by

$$dX (t) = a (t) X (t) dt + b (t) X (t) dW (t) ; \tag{15}$$

where a, b : [0; T] → R are some functions (as in the introduction). We interpret a (t) as the interest rate and b (t) as the volatility, that is the strength of fluctuations in the market. The price of a European call option for the share X can be found by the Black-Scholes equation.

Theorem :

The price p (t; x) of a European call option for a share satisfying (10) with initial condition X (t) = x, is given by the partial differential equation

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t}(t, x) + a(t)x \frac{\partial p}{\partial t}(t, x) + \frac{(b(t)x)^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} a(t)p(t, x), \text{ for } 0 < t < T, x \in R \\ p(t, x) = (x - k)^+ \text{ for } x \in R \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

Here K is the pre-specified price, for which the owner of the option may purchase one unit of the stock X at time T.

Proof:

For simplicity, we prove this theorem in the case of constant a and b. The proof is

similar for non-constant a and b . Let X be given by (1) and assume the existence of a risk-free paper B satisfying

$$dB(t) = aB(t) dt \tag{17}$$

Consider the portfolio replicating the option

$$I(t) = -p(t, X(t)) + \alpha(t) X(t) + \beta(t) B(t), \tag{18}$$

for some $\alpha(t), \beta(t) \in \mathbb{R}$. We assume that the portfolio is self-financing in the sense that no money is brought in or taken out of the portfolio. Mathematically, this can be written

$$d(\alpha(t)X(t) + \beta(t)B(t)) = \alpha(t) dX(t) + \beta(t) dB(t), \tag{19}$$

for the portfolio $\alpha(t)X(t) + \beta(t)B(t)$. For notational clarity we suppress the evaluation point $(t; X(t))$ in the calculations below. Applying the Itô formula to $I(t)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} dI(t) &= -dp + d(\alpha(t)X(t) + \beta(t)B(t)) \\ &= -\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} dt - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} dX(t) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} (dX(t))^2 + \alpha(t)dX(t) + \beta(t)dB(t) \\ &= \left(-\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} aX(t) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} b^2(X(t))^2 + \alpha(t)aX(t) + \beta(t)aB(t) \right) dt \\ &\quad + \left(\alpha(t) - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) bX(t)dw(t) \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Now choose $\alpha(t)$ so that the portfolio becomes riskless (only the deterministic part remains).

This can be achieved by setting $\alpha(t) = \frac{\partial p}{\partial x}$, Then

$$\begin{aligned} dI(t) &= \left(-\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} aX(t) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} b^2(X(t))^2 + \alpha(t)aX(t) + \beta(t)aB(t) \right) dt \\ &= \left(-\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} b^2(X(t))^2 + \beta(t)aB(t) \right) dt \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

If we now suppose that the opportunity of arbitrage is precluded, so that the probability of gaining money without risk is zero, then $I(t)$, being riskless, must evolve as the risk-free paper B . Hence $dI(t) = aI(t) dt$ and, by combining (18) and (21), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\left(-\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} b^2(X(t))^2 + \beta(t)aB(t) \right) dt \\ &= dI(t) = aI(t) dt = a(-p + \alpha(t)X(t) + \beta(t)B(t)) dt \\ &= a \left(-p + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} X(t) + \beta(t)B(t) \right) dt \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

which, after rearranging the terms and setting $x = X(t)$, reduces to the partial differential equation

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + ax \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} b^2 x^2 \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = ap \tag{23}$$

for $t < T$, where T is the exercise time of the option. At time T the cost of exercising the option is K so the terminal condition corresponding to (23) must be

$$p(T, x) = (x - K)^+, \tag{24}$$

which completes the proof.*

For non-constant a and b we cannot be certain that there exists a analytical solution to the Black-Scholes equation and to determine the option price we use the representation formula supplied by the Feynman-Kac formula derived in the next section.

Relating Stochastic and partial differential equations:

In this section we find a way to represent the solution to the following partial differential equation with prescribed terminal value

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial F}{\partial t}(t, x) + AF(t, x) = 0 & \text{for } 0 < t < T, x \in R \\ F(T, x) = \phi(x), & \text{for } x \in R \end{cases} \tag{25}$$

$$AF(t, x) = \mu(t, x) \frac{\partial F}{\partial x}(t, x) + \frac{1}{2}(\sigma(t, x))^2 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(t, x) \tag{26}$$

in terms of stochastic differential equations. Let F be a solution to (25), x the point (t, x) and define X to be the stochastic differential equation

$$dX(s) = \mu(s, X(s)) ds + \sigma(s, X(s)) dw(s) \tag{27}$$

with initial value $X(t) = x$. We apply the Itô formula to $F(s, X(s))$ and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & F(T, X(T)) - F(t, X(t)) \\ &= \int_t^T dF(s, X(s)) \\ &= \int_t^T \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial s}(s, X(s)) + \mu(s, X(s)) \frac{\partial F}{\partial x}(s, X(s)) + \frac{1}{2}(\sigma(s, X(s)))^2 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(s, X(s)) \right) ds \\ &\quad + \int_t^T (\sigma(s, X(s)) \frac{\partial F}{\partial x}(s, X(s))) dw(s) \\ &= \int_t^T \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial s}(s, X(s)) + AF(s, X(s)) \right) ds + \int_t^T (\sigma(s, X(s)) \frac{\partial F}{\partial x}(s, X(s))) dw(s) \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

F is the solution to (25), so (28) reduces to

$$\phi(X(T)) - F(t, x) = \int_t^T (\sigma(s, X(s)) \frac{\partial F}{\partial x}(s, X(s))) dw(s) \tag{29}$$

Taking expectations of both sides, we deduce

$$F(t, x) = E^{t,x} [\phi(X(T))], \tag{30}$$

where the indices t, x means that the process X satisfies $X(t) = x$. Formula (30) represents the solution to (25) as an expectation of a function of the solution to a stochastic differential equation.

Similarly we can show that the solution to the partial differential equation

$$(31) \quad \begin{cases} \frac{\partial F}{\partial t}(t, x) + AF(t, x) - q(t, x)F(t, x) = 0 & \text{for } 0 < t < T, x \in R \\ F(T, x) = \phi(x), & \text{for } x \in R \end{cases}$$

Is given by

$$F(t, x) = E^{t,x} \left[\phi[X(T)] \exp \left(- \int_t^T q(s, X(s)) ds \right) \right] \quad (32)$$

where X satisfies (27). This result is known as the Feynman-Kac formula.

Comparing (31) with A as in (26) to the Black-Scholes equation (16), it is clear that the two partial differential equations coincide if we set $F(t, x) = p(t, x)$, $\Phi(x) = (x - K)^+$, $\mu(t, x) = a(t)$, $\sigma(t, x) = b(t)x$ and $q(t, x) = a(t)$. Hence, the Feynman-Kac formula can be used to represent the option price.

For constant a and b, we have

$$p(t, x) = E^{t,x} \left[(X(T) - k)^+ \exp(-a(T-t)) \right] \quad (33)$$

Since X is a geometric Brownian motion, whose exact solution is known and was derived in, we can calculate p(t, x) as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} p(t, x) &= E \left[\left(x \exp \left(\left(a - \frac{1}{2} b^2 \right) (T-t) + bW(T-t) \right) - k \right)^+ \exp(-a(T-t)) \right] \quad (34) \\ &= \int_R \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi(T-t)}} \exp \left(-\frac{y^2}{2(T-t)} \right) \left(x \exp \left(\left(a - \frac{1}{2} b^2 \right) (T-t) + by \right) - k \right)^+ \exp(-a(T-t)) dy \end{aligned}$$

(35)

where the density of a Wiener process was used in the last step.

References

- [1] Gihman I.I., Skorohod A.V. "Stochastic differential equations" Moscow, 1968
- [2] Vatanabe, Ikeda "Stochastic differential equations and diffusion processes"
- [3] Jonathan Goodman, Kyoung-Sook Moon, Anders Szepessy, Raúl Tempone, and Georgios Zouraris. Stochastic and Partial Differential Equations with Adaptive Numerics. Technical report, Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), Stockholm, Sweden, 2006.
- [4] Peter E. Kloeden and Eckhard Platen. Numerical Solution of Stochastic Differential Equations. Springer 1992
- [5] Bernt Oksendal. Stochastic Differential Equations, An Introduction with Applications.

Springer, 5th edition, 1998.

- [6] Swishchuk A.V., Kazmerchuk Y.I. "Stability of stochastic differential delay ITO's equations with poison jumps and with Markovian switchings, application to Financial models
- [7] Timothy Sauer, Numerical Solution of Stochastic Differential Equations in Finance, Department of Mathematics George Mason University
- [8] 1Abodolsadeh Neisy and 2Moslem Peymany, Financial Modeling by Ordinary and Stochastic Differential Equations
- [9] Zenghu Li, Stochastic differential equations with applications in finance
- [10] y Richard F. Bass , Stochastic differential equations with jumps; Department of Mathematics, University of Connecticut
- [11] Zhenting Hou, Jiaowan Luo, Peng Shi, and Sing Kiong Nguang, Stochastic Stability of Ito Differential Equations With Semi-Markovian Jump Parameters
- [12] Nakao, S. On the pathwise uniqueness of solutions of one-dimensional stochastic differential equations. Osaka J. Math. 9 (1972), 513{518. MR326840